

Conductometric and Viscometric Investigations of Yttrium Carboxylates in Mixed Organic Solvents

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Yttrium carboxylates (butyrate, valerate and caproate) behave as weak electrolyte in dilute solutions and the CMC decreases with increasing chainlength of fatty acid constituent of the molecule. The CMC, degree of dissociation and dissociation constant of yttrium carboxylates in a mixture of benzene and dimethylformamide (60 : 40, v/v) have been evaluated from conductometric measurements. The viscosity results are explained on the basis of equation proposed by Einstein, Vand, Moulik and Jones-Dole. The values of the molar volume calculated by the equations of Einstein and Vand are in agreement.

THE study of carboxylates of scandium, yttrium and lanthanum has been a subject of intense investigations. The preparation and thermal decomposition of these carboxylates have been reviewed by several workers¹. The preparation, spectral, thermal and solution properties of scandium and lanthanum carboxylates have been reported². Mehrotra *et al.*³ prepared mono-, di- and tricarboxylates of yttrium by the reaction of yttrium isopropoxide with acids or acid anhydrides. Dabkowska⁴ carried out the derivatographic studies of the thermal decomposition of yttrium formate and found that the formate dihydrate loses water of crystallisation at 100–10° and is stable upto 250°. Turcotte *et al.*⁵ and Corter *et al.*⁶ pointed out that the crystals of anhydrous formate of yttrium possess rhombohedral symmetry while that of the hydrated formate possess orthorhombic symmetry. Pogodilova *et al.*⁷ and Antsyshkina *et al.*⁸ reported the formation of yttrium formate with neutral donor ligands.

The physicochemical characteristics and structure of metal carboxylates largely depend on the method of preparation and so it is desirable to study the properties of these carboxylates in solid state and in solutions. The carboxylates (butyrate, valerate and caproate) of yttrium possess low solubility in pure organic solvents and so the properties (conductivity and viscosity) have been investigated in a mixture of benzene and dimethylformamide (60 : 40, v/v). The work has been initiated with a view to study the structural changes in solutions, critical micelle concentration and solute-solvent interactions.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Yttrium carboxylates (butyrate, valerate and caproate) were prepared by direct metathesis of

the corresponding potassium salt with aqueous solution of yttrium nitrate at 50–55°. The purity of these carboxylates was checked by the elemental analysis and ir spectra.

A Toshniwal CL 01.10A digital conductivity meter, a dipping type conductivity cell with platinised electrodes, a dilatometer and a viscometer of Ostwald's type were used. All the measurements were made at 40±0.05°.

Results and Discussion

Conductivity: The increase in specific conductance with increasing concentration (Fig. 1) may be due to the ionisation of yttrium carboxylate into simple metal cations, Y³⁺ and fatty acid anions, RCOO⁻ in solutions. It is suggested that the anions begin to aggregate to form micelles at the CMC. The rate of increase of specific conductance with increasing concentration above the CMC than below, is contrary to normal behaviour which cannot be explained. The decrease in specific conductance with increasing chainlength of the carboxylate molecules may be due to the increasing size and decreasing mobility of anions with increasing chainlength of fatty acid radical constituent of carboxylate molecules.

The decrease in the molar conductance (μ) with increasing concentration of yttrium carboxylate may be due to the combined effects of ionic atmosphere, solvation of ions, decrease of mobility and ionisation and formation of micelles. An expression for the dissociation of yttrium carboxylates can be developed in Ostwald's manner,

where C is the concentration (mol dm⁻³), α the degree of dissociation and R is C₃H₇, C₄H₉ and C₅H₁₁ for butyrate, valerate and caproate, respec-

tively. The dissociation constant (K) can be expressed as

$$K = \frac{Y^{3+} RCOO^-)^3}{Y(RCOO)_3} = \frac{27C^3\alpha^4}{1-\alpha} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Specific conductance vs concentration of yttrium carboxylates in a mixture of 60% benzene and 40% dimethylformamide: (▲) butyrate, (○) valerate and (Δ) caproate.

Fig. 2. Viscosity vs concentration of yttrium carboxylates in a mixture of 60% benzene and 40% dimethylformamide: (▲) butyrate, (○) valerate and (Δ) caproate.

Since the ionic concentrations are low and so the interionic effects being almost negligible, the solutions will not deviate appreciably from the ideal behaviour and therefore the activity of ions can be taken as almost equal to their concentrations. The degree of dissociation (α) may be

replaced by the conductance ratio, μ/μ_0 , where μ is the molar conductance at finite concentration and μ_0 the limiting molar conductance at infinite dilution. On substituting the value of α and rearranging, equation (1) can be expressed as

$$\mu^3 C^3 = \frac{K\mu_0^4}{27\mu} - \frac{K\mu_0^3}{27} \quad (2)$$

The values of K and μ_0 (14.3, 13.6 and 13.3 for butyrate, valerate and caproate, respectively) were obtained from the slopes and intercepts of the linear portion of the plots of $\mu^3 C^3$ vs $1/\mu$. It was found that the values of K decrease with increasing chainlength of the carboxylate molecules. The values of α for these carboxylates lie in the range 0.22–0.38 which indicates that they behave as weak electrolytes in solutions.

Density and viscosity: The density (ρ), viscosity (η) and specific viscosity (η_{sp}) of the solutions of yttrium carboxylates in a mixture of benzene and dimethylformamide (60 : 40, v/v) increase with increasing concentration of the carboxylates. The plots of η vs C (Fig. 2) are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite concentration corresponding to the CMC. The viscosity results confirm that there is no appreciable aggregation of the carboxylate molecules below the CMC whereas there is a sudden increase in the aggregation at this concentration. The viscosity results have been interpreted in the light of equations proposed by Einstein⁹, Vand¹⁰, Moulik¹¹ and Jones-Dole¹².

The plots of η_{sp} vs C are linear below the CMC with intercepts almost equal to zero, which shows that the Einstein's equation is applicable to these solutions. The values of the molar volume (\bar{V}) of the carboxylates (Table 1) obtained from the slopes of the plots of Vand's equation [$1/C$ vs $1/\log(\eta/\eta_0)$] are in close agreement with the values obtained from Einstein's equation. The plots of η_{sp}/C vs C below the CMC have been extrapolated to zero carboxylate concentration and the extrapolated values (i.e the intrinsic viscosity, η_I) increase with increasing chainlength of the carboxylate molecules (Table 1).

The values of the constants A and B of the Jones-Dole's equation calculated from the intercept and slope of the plots of η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} vs \sqrt{C} below the CMC are recorded in Table 1. The values of B (solute-solvent interaction), are larger than those of A (solute-solute interaction), which confirms that the molecules of yttrium carboxylates in solutions do not show appreciable aggregation below the CMC and there is marked change in the aggregation of the molecules at the CMC. The values of Moulik's constants, M and K (Table 1) obtained from the intercept and slope of the plots of $(\eta/\eta_0)^3$ vs C^3 increase with increasing chainlength of fatty acid constituent of carboxylate molecules. The values of the CMC obtained from the viscosity and conductivity measurements are in agreement.

TABLE I - VALUES OF VARIOUS PARAMETERS FROM VISCOSITY MEASUREMENTS OF YTTRIUM CARBOXYLATES IN A MIXTURE OF BENZENE-DIMETHYLFORMAMIDE AT $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$

Yttrium carboxylates	CMC $\times 10_3$ mol dm $^{-3}$	\bar{V} (dm 3 mol $^{-1}$)		ϕ	M	K	A	B	η_1
		(Einstein eqn.)	(Vand eqn.)						
Butyrate	19.0	0.23	0.27	8	1.029	143	0.14	0.30	0.005
Valerate	18.0	0.29	0.31	7	1.035	183	0.25	0.38	0.008
Caproate	13.5	0.37	0.34	6	1.042	200	0.28	1.07	0.009

It is concluded that the viscosity results for the solutions of yttrium carboxylates may be satisfactorily explained in terms of equations proposed by Einstein, Vand, Moulik and Jones-Dole.

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